

A STUDY ON RINGED AUTOMATA SPACE OVER BOOLEAN AUTOMATA SPACE

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Abstract : We first presented in this paper sheaf of rings over a topological automata space X , ringed automata spaces, partition property of a Boolean automata space (totally disconnected; compact hausdorff topological automata space), theorems related to sheaves of rings over a Boolean automata space, in a ringed automata space over Boolean automata space, the ring of global sections is commutative if each stalk is commutative, one-one correspondence between the class of completely prime ideals of a near-ring N generated by automaton and prime ideals of its Boolean ring $B(N)$ generated by automaton.

Keywords : Sheaf of Rings, Topological Automata Space, Boolean Automata Space.

Ring Automaton Space: Let X be a topological space over Automata (TSA). Suppose that for each automaton x in X , a ring R_x with zero 0_x and identity 1_x

Assume $R_x \cap R_y = \emptyset$ for automata $x \neq y$.

Let $R = \cup R_x$. Denote $\Pi : R \rightarrow X$ by $\Pi(r) = x$ if $r \in R_x$ for automaton x .

Assume that a topology is imposed on R such that the following axioms are satisfied:

- I. If $r \in R$, $\exists$ open sets U in R with $r \in U$, $N \subseteq X$ such that $\Pi : U \rightarrow N$ is homeomorphic.
- II. Let $R + R = \{(r,s) / \Pi(r) = \Pi(s)\}$ with the topology induced the product topology y in $R \times R$. Then the mapping $r \rightarrow -r$ is continuous on R to R and the mappings $(r, s) \rightarrow r + s$, $(r, s) \rightarrow rs$ and continuous on $R+R$ to R .
- III. The mapping $x \rightarrow 1_x$ is continuous on X to R .

With these conditions R is called sheaf automata of rings over topological space over Automata X . The automata of rings R_x are called the stalks of the sheaf automata R . The pair (X, R) is called a ring automaton space.

Subsheaf automata: Suppose R is a sheaf automaton of rings over Automata Space X . A subset of R^1 of R is a subsheaf automata of R if R^1 is an open subset of R and $R^1 \cap R_x$ is a subringed automaton space of R_x for each for automaton x . Then R^1 is a sheaf automata of rings over X .

Definition: Let R be a sheaf of rings over Automata Space X . Let U be a subset of Automata Space X . A section of R over U is a continuous mapping σ of U to R such that $\Pi \circ \sigma = \text{id}_U$. The collection of section of R over U is denoted $\Gamma(U)$.

Lemma: Let R be a sheaf of rings over an Automata Space X .

- (a). The mapping $\Pi : R \rightarrow X$ is open and continuous.
- (b). $\Gamma(U)$ is a ring Automata Space X with point wise operations $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)(x) = \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x)$, $(\sigma_1 \sigma_2)(x) = \sigma_1(x) \sigma_2(x)$, $0(x) = 0_x$, and $1(x) = 1_x$.
- (c). Let $r \in R_x$. Then $\exists$ a nbd N of X and $\sigma \in \Gamma(N)$ such that $\sigma(x) = r$.
- (d). Let $x \in U \subseteq X$ and suppose that $\sigma_1 \in \Gamma(U)$, $\sigma_2 \in \Gamma(U)$ satisfy $\sigma_1(x) = \sigma_2(x)$. Then $\exists$ a nbd N of Automata Space X such that $\sigma_1(y) = \sigma_2(y)$ for all $y \in N \cap U$.

Proof: (a). $\Pi : R \rightarrow X$. Let N_1 be an open set of the Automata Space X

Let $r \in \Pi^{-1}(N_1) \Rightarrow \Pi(r) \in N$. Since $r \in R \exists$ an open set U of R and open set N_2 is homeo and $U \cap \Pi^{-1}(N_2) \subseteq \Pi^{-1}(N_1)$. $\therefore \Pi$ is continuous.

Π is open map : Let W be an open set in R and $x \in \Pi(W)$. Let $e \in W \ni \Pi(e) = x$. Since $e \in R$, so $\exists$ a nbd $W^1 \subseteq W$ & $e \in W^1$ mapped by Π onto an open set in Automata Space X i.e Automata x has a nbd $\Pi(W^1)$ inside $\Pi(W)$.
 $\therefore \Pi$ is open map.

- (b). Let $\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in \Gamma(U) \Rightarrow \sigma_1, \sigma_2 : U \rightarrow R$
 $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)(x) = \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x)$
 $(\sigma_1 \sigma_2)(x) = \sigma_1(x) \sigma_2(x)$
 $0(x) = 0_x, 1(x) = 1_x \quad \forall x \in U.$
 $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2 : U \rightarrow R$

Let W be a nbd in R .

Consider $(\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)^{-1}(W)$

Let $x \in (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)^{-1}(W)$
 $\Rightarrow (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)(x) \in W$
 $\Rightarrow \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x) \in W$

Claim: $\sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ is continuous.

Let W open in R . Let $x \in (\sigma_1 + \sigma_2)^{-1}(W) \Rightarrow \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x) \in W$.

Since $+$: $R \times R \rightarrow R$ is continuous and W nbd in R

$\Rightarrow +^{-1}(W)$ is open in $R \times R$.

Since $(\sigma_1(x), \sigma_2(x)) \in +^{-1}(W)$

$\exists W_1$ nbd of $\sigma_1(x), W_2$ nbd of $\sigma_2(x) \ni W_1 \times W_2 \in +^{-1}(W)$

$\Rightarrow + (W_1 \times W_2) \subseteq W$ and $W_1 + W_2$ is nbd of $\sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x)$.

$\therefore \sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ is continuous.

Ill^y $\sigma_1 \sigma_2, 0(x) = 0_x, 1(x) = 1_x$ are continuous.

(c). Let $r \in R_x \Rightarrow r \in R \Rightarrow \exists$ open sets U in R with $r \in U$, and $N \subseteq X$.

$\Pi : U \rightarrow N$ is homeomorphism.

Let $\sigma = (\Pi/U)^{-1} : N \rightarrow U \subseteq R \Rightarrow \sigma \in \Gamma(N)$.

Since $\Pi(r) = x \Rightarrow (\Pi/U)^{-1}(x) = r$
 $\Rightarrow \sigma(x) = r.$

(d). Suppose N is open & $\sigma \in \Gamma(N)$.

$\Rightarrow \Pi \circ \sigma = id_N$

$\Rightarrow \sigma$ is one-one and $\sigma^{-1} = \Pi/\sigma(N)$.

Let $x \in N$ and choose a nbd U of $\sigma(x)$ in R such that the maps U homeomorphically on a nbd of automata x in Automata Space X . But the continuity of $\sigma, \sigma^{-1} (U \cap \sigma(N)) = \sigma^{-1} (U)$ is nbd M of x . Then $\sigma(M) = (\Pi/U)^{-1}(M)$ is open.

Since x is arbitrary, $\sigma(N)$ is open.

$\therefore 0(x) = \{ 0_x / x \in X \}$ is open.

(e). Let $x \in U \subseteq X$ and $\sigma_1 \in \Gamma(U), \sigma_2 \in \Gamma(U) \ni \sigma_1(x) = \sigma_2(x)$

Since $\Pi \sigma_1(x) = \Pi \sigma_2(x)$

$\Rightarrow (\sigma_1(x), \sigma_2(x)) \in R + R$ & $+$ is continuous on $R + R \ni$ nbd N of $x \ni \sigma_1(y) = \sigma_2(y) \forall y \in N \cap U$.

Property: Partition property of a Boolean space:

If X is a Boolean Automaton space (totally disconnected compact hausdorff automaton space), and $\{N_i / i \in I\}$ is an open covering of X , then $\exists \{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}$, a finite set of clopen subsets of Automata Space X , such that

(i) for every $j \leq r, \exists I \in I \ni M_j \subseteq N_i$.

(ii) $M_i \cap M_j = \emptyset$ if $i \neq j$

(iii) $\bigcup_{i=1}^r M_i = X$

The Collection $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}$ of open closed subsets is called a partition of Automata Space X .

Note: (1) If $\sigma \in \Gamma(U)$ & $V \subseteq U$, then $\sigma/V \in \Gamma(V)$.

(2). If U_1, U_2 are subsets of X with $U_1 \cap U_2 = \emptyset$, and if $\sigma_i \in \Gamma(U_i)$, then $\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2 \in \Gamma(U_1 \cup U_2)$ when $(\sigma_1 \cup \sigma_2)(y) = \sigma_i(y)$ if $y \in U_i$

$= \sigma_2(y)$ if $y \in U_2$.

Theorem: Let R be a sheaf of rings over a Boolean Automata Space X . Let U be a closed subset of Automata Space X and suppose that $\sigma \in \Gamma(U)$. Then there exists $\tau \in \Gamma(X)$ such that $\tau|_U = \sigma$

Proof: Let $x \in X$. Suppose $x \notin U$, $\exists$ nbd N_x of $x \ni U \cap N_x = \emptyset$.

$$\therefore X = \bigcup_{x \in X} N_x$$

By the partition property $\exists$ a finite set $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}$ of clopen sets in $X \ni$ (i). $M_j \cap M_k = \emptyset$ for $j \neq k$.

(iii) $\bigcup_{i=1}^r M_i = X$, and for each j , either $M_j \cap Y = \emptyset$ or $\exists \tau_j \in \Gamma(M_j) \ni$

$\tau_j(y) = \sigma(y) \quad \forall y \in M_j \cap Y$. If $M_j \cap Y = \emptyset$, let $\tau_j(y) = 0_y$ for all $y \in M_j$

Let $\tau = \tau_1 \cup \tau_2 \cup \dots \cup \tau_r$. Then $\tau \in \Gamma(X)$ and $\tau|_U = \sigma$.

Note: X is a Boolean Automata Space. R is a sheaf of rings over Automata Space. The mapping from $\Gamma(X, R) \rightarrow R_x$ is an epimorphism $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma(x)$.

Let $r \in R_x \Rightarrow r \in R$.

Let $U = \{x\} \subseteq X \Rightarrow U$ is closed set in X & put $\sigma^1(z) = r$.

$\Rightarrow \exists \sigma \in \Gamma(x) \ni \sigma|_U = \sigma^1$ i.e $\sigma(x) = \sigma^1(x) = r$.

$|\sigma| \rightarrow \sigma(x)$ is an epimorphism.

Definition: A ringed Automata space (X, R) will be called reduced if

(i) X is Boolean Automata space.

(ii) If $\sigma \in B(\Sigma(X))$, then for all $x \in X$, either $\sigma(x) = 0_x$ or $\sigma(x) = 1_x$.

Theorem: Suppose (X, r) is a Ringed Automata Space with X a Boolean Automata space if R_x is commutative $\forall x \in X$ then $\Gamma(X)$ is commutative over Automata Space X .

Proof: Suppose is commutative $\forall$ automata $x \in X$.

Let $\sigma_1, \sigma_2 \in \Gamma(X)$.

$\sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x) - \sigma_1(x) - \sigma_2(x) = 0 \quad \exists$ nbd M_x of $x \ni$

$\sigma_1(y) + \sigma_2(y) - \sigma_1(y) - \sigma_2(y) = 0 \quad \forall y \in M_x$.

Since $X = \bigcup_{x \in X} M_x$

Since X is Boolean automata space, by finite partition of automata space X , $\exists$ a finite family $\{M_1, M_2, \dots, M_r\}$ of pair wise disjoint, clopen sets with

$\sigma_1(y) + \sigma_2(y) - \sigma_1(y) - \sigma_2(y) = 0 \quad \forall y \in M_y$.

$\therefore \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x) - \sigma_1(x) - \sigma_2(x) = 0 \quad \forall x \in X$.

$\therefore \sigma_1(x) + \sigma_2(x) = \sigma_2(x) + \sigma_1(x) \quad \forall x \in X$.

$\therefore \sigma_1 + \sigma_2 = \sigma_2 + \sigma_1$

$\therefore \Gamma(X)$ is commutative.

Lemma : Let (X, R) be commutative ringed space with X is a Boolean Automata space. Then

(1). If for all x , R_x is indecomposable, then (X, R) is reduced.

(2). If for all x , R_x is commutative and (X, R) is reduced then $\forall x$, R_x is indecomposable.

Proof: $B(\Gamma(X)) = \{ \sigma / \sigma : X \rightarrow R \text{ is continuous and } \sigma^2 = \sigma \}$.

Since $\sigma \rightarrow \sigma(x)$ is an epimorphism from $\Gamma(X)$ onto R_x .

Since $\sigma^2 = \sigma \Rightarrow \sigma(x) \in B(R(x))$.

Since R_x is indecomposable, $B(R_x) = \{ 0_x, 1_x \}$.

If $\sigma \in B(\Gamma(X)) \Rightarrow \sigma(x) = 0_x$ or $\sigma(x) = 1_x$.

$\therefore (X, R)$ is reduced.

Suppose R_x is commutative $\forall x$ and (X, R) is reduced. Then $\Gamma(X)$ is commutative.

Claim: R_x is indecomposable.

Suppose some R_y is decomposable, so $\exists$ an idempotent $e_y \ni e_y \neq 0_y, 1_y$.

Define $\sigma^1 : \{y\} \rightarrow R$ by $\sigma^1(y) = e_y$. Then $\exists$ a clopen set N of $y \ni \tau \in \Gamma(N) \ni \tau(y) = e_y$ & $(\tau^2 - \tau)(x) = 1_x \quad \forall x \in N$.

Define $\sigma : X \rightarrow R$ by $\sigma(x) = \tau(x) \quad \forall x \in N$
 $\sigma(x) = 0_x \quad \forall x \in X - N.$
 $\Rightarrow \sigma \in B(\Gamma(X))$ & $\sigma(y) \neq 0_y, \sigma(y) \neq 1_y.$
 $\therefore (X, R)$ is not reduced. It is a contradiction.
 $\therefore R_x$ is indecomposable $\forall x \in X.$

Remark : Throughout this chapter hereafter we assume that N is a p -near-ring (p is prime) with identity generated by automaton. For p -near-rings with identity we know that

- (1) $(N, +)$ is a commutative group.
- (2) All idempotents are central.
- (3) N contains a family of completely prime ideals with trivial intersection.

When I, I^1 are ideals of N , then $I \cap I^1, I \cup I^1$ are ideals of N , then $\sum I_\alpha$ is an ideal of N . The set $B(N)$ of all idempotents of N are central. $B(N)$ is a Boolean ring with $ee^1 = ee^1$ and $e \oplus e^1 = e + e^1 - ee^1$. And the set $\text{spec } B(N)$ of all prime ideals is a topological automata space with hull-kernel topology. $\text{Spec } B(N)$ is totally disconnected compact Hausdorff automata space. Hereafter N stands for p -near-ring generated by automaton

- Lemma:** (1). If I, I^1 are ideals of N , then $I \cap I^1, I \cup I^1$ are ideals of N .
 (2). If $\{I_\alpha/\alpha \in \Delta\}$ is a family of ideals of N , then $\sum I_\alpha$ is an ideal of N .

Proof: Clearly $I \cap I^1$ is an ideal of N .

- (1). Claim: $I \cap I^1$ are ideals of N . Let $\sum a_i b_i, \sum a_i^1 b_i^1$ be elements of I, I^1

with $a_i, a_i^1 \in I, b_i, b_i^1 \in I^1.$
 $\sum a_i b_i - \sum a_i^1 b_i^1 = \sum a_i b_i + \sum a_i^1 (-b_i^1)$ is in $I \cap I^1$, so $I \cap I^1$ is group under $+$.
 Let $n \in N. (\sum a_i b_i) n = \sum a_i^1 (-b_i^1 n) \in I \cap I^1$
 Let $z = \sum a_i b_i$ be an element in $I \cap I^1$.
 Since $z^p = z$, so $z^{p-1} \in B(N) \cap I \cap I^1$.
 By pierce decomposition theorem.

$$N \cong N z^{p-1} + N(z^{p-1} - 1)$$

Denote z^{p-1} by e .

Let $x, y \in N$.

Consider $[y(z+x) - yx](e-1)$
 $[y(z+x) - yx](e-1) = y(ze + x)(e-1) - yx(e-1)$
 $= yx(e-1) - yx(e-1)$
 $= 0$

$\Rightarrow y(z+x) - yx \in Ne$, which is in $I \cap I^1$.
 $\therefore I \cap I^1$ is an ideal of N .

- (2) Claim: $\sum I_\alpha$ is an ideal of N .

Let $\sum a_{\alpha i}, \sum b_{\alpha j}$ be two elements of $\sum I_\alpha$ where $a_{\alpha i} \in I_{\alpha i}, b_{\alpha j} \in I_{\alpha j}.$
 $\sum a_{\alpha i} - \sum b_{\alpha j} = \sum a_{\alpha i} + \sum (-b_{\alpha j}) \in \sum I_\alpha.$
 $\therefore \sum I_\alpha$ is a group.

Let $n \in N. (\sum a_{\alpha i})n = \sum a_{\alpha i} n \in \sum I_\alpha. \text{ Let } z = \sum a_{\alpha i} \in \sum I_\alpha.$

Let $e = z^{p-1}$. Let $x, y \in N$ and $[y(z+x) - yx](e-1) = 0$
 $\Rightarrow y(z+x) - yx \in Ne \subseteq \sum I_\alpha.$

$\therefore \sum I_\alpha$ is an ideal of N .

Corollary: $B(N)$ is a set of idempotents of p -near-ring N generated by automaton then $B(N)$ is a Boolean ring generated by automata where $\oplus$ and $\ominus$ defined by $e \oplus f = e + f - ef$ and $e \ominus f = ef \quad \forall e, f \in B(N).$

Definition: An ideal I is called regular if $I = N [I \cap B(N)]$.

Lemma: Every ideal I of N is regular.

Proof: Let $a \neq 0 \in I \Rightarrow a^{p-1} = e$ is an idempotent.
 $\Rightarrow e$ is central.

$\therefore$ For $n \in N, e_n = n^{p-1} \in B(N)$.
 $\therefore I \cap B(N) = \{ e_n / n \in I \}$.
 $\therefore$ For any $n \neq 0$ in $I, n^p = n$ so $n = n \cdot e_n \in N (I \cap B(N))$
 $\therefore I \subseteq N(I \cap B(N))$

Clearly $N(I \cap B(N)) \subseteq I$

For let $n \in N$ and $e \in I \cap B(N)$

Consider $n(0 + e) - n0 \in I$

$\Rightarrow ne - 0 \in I$ (since $n0 = 0$ & $N \in \eta_0$)

$\Rightarrow ne \in I$

$\therefore I = N(I \cap B(N))$

$\therefore I$ is regular.

Theorem: Let Π be the set of completely prime ideals of N generated by automata and $\Gamma(I) = \{ p \in \Pi / I \text{ an ideal of } N \text{ with } I \not\subseteq P \}$. Then Π is a topological automata space with a basic open set $\Gamma(I)$ for all ideals I of N .

Proof; Suppose I and I^1 are ideals of N generated by automata.

Claim: $\Gamma(I) \cap \Gamma(I^1) = \Gamma(I I^1)$

$P \in \Gamma(I) \cap \Gamma(I^1) \iff P \in \Gamma(I) \text{ and } P \in \Gamma(I^1)$
 $\iff I \not\subseteq P \text{ and } I^1 \not\subseteq P$
 $\iff I I^1 \not\subseteq P$
 $\iff P \in \Gamma(I I^1)$

Suppose $\{I_\alpha / \alpha \in \Delta\}$ is a family of ideals of N

Claim: $\bigcup_{\alpha \in \Delta} \Gamma(I_\alpha) = \Gamma(\sum I_\alpha)$

$P \in \bigcup_{\alpha \in \Delta} \Gamma(I_\alpha) \iff P \in \Gamma(I_\alpha) \text{ for some } \alpha \in \Delta$

$\iff I_\alpha \not\subseteq P \text{ for some } \alpha \in \Delta$
 $\iff \sum I_\alpha \not\subseteq P$
 $\iff P \in \Gamma(\sum I_\alpha)$
 $\therefore \bigcup_{\alpha \in \Delta} \Gamma(I_\alpha) = \Gamma(\sum I_\alpha)$

$\therefore \Pi$ is a topological automata space for which $\{\Gamma(I) / I \text{ an ideal of } N\}$ is an open base. And clearly $\Gamma(0) = \Pi, \Gamma(N) = \phi$.

Theorem: The topological automata space Π is homomorphic with space $\text{Spec } B(N)$ of N .

Proof: Suppose N is a p -near-ring. Then $B(N)$ is a Boolean. $\text{Spec } B(N)$ the set of all prime ideals of $B(N)$ is a totally disconnected Hausdorff space. Since already proved every ideal of N is a regular ideal of N , every completely prime ideal P of N can be written as $P = N(P \cap B(N))$.

$\therefore$ For every prime ideal $x \in X$ (hereafter we denote $\text{Spec } B(N)$ by X)

Nx is a completely prime ideal of N ($Nx \in \Pi$).

Now we define $F : \Pi \rightarrow X$ by $F(P) = P \cap B(N)$.

Since P is a completely prime ideal of $N, P \cap B(N)$ is a prime ideal of $B(N)$.

$\therefore P \cap B(N) \in X$

Suppose $F(P) = F(P^1)$

$\Rightarrow P \cap B(N) = P^1 \cap B(N)$

$a \in P \iff a^{p-1} \in P \cap B(N)$

since a^{p-1} is an idempotent.

$\iff a^{p-1} \in P^1 \cap B(N)$

$\iff a^{p-1} \in P^1$

$\iff a = a^p = a^{p-1}a \in P^1$.

$\therefore P = P^1$.

$\therefore F(P) = F(P^1) \Rightarrow P = P^1$.

$\therefore F$ is one- one.

Suppose x is a prime ideal in $B(N)$.

Claim: Nx is a completely prime ideal of N generated by automata x

Clearly Nx is an ideal in N

Suppose $nn_1 \in Nx$ for any $n, n_1 \in N$.

Suppose $n \notin Nx$ and $n_1 \notin Nx$
 $\Rightarrow nn^{p-1} \notin Nx$ and $n_1n_1^{p-1} \notin Nx$
 $\Rightarrow n^{p-1} \notin x$ and $n_1^{p-1} \notin x$
 $\Rightarrow n^{p-1}n_1^{p-1} \notin x$
 $\Rightarrow n^{p-1}n_1^{p-1} \oplus x = B(N)$
 $\therefore 1 = n^{p-1}n_1^{p-1} \oplus s^1$ for some $s, s^1 \in B(N)$ with $s^1 \in X$.
 $\Rightarrow N = N n^{p-1}n_1^{p-1} \oplus x$, it is a contradiction to $N n^{p-1}n_1^{p-1} \subseteq Nn_1 \subseteq Nx$
 $\therefore Nx$ is a completely prime ideal.
 $\therefore Nx \in \Pi$
 $F(Nx) = Nx \cap B(N) = x$ in X
 $\therefore F$ is onto.
 Now consider $n \in N, \Gamma(n)$
 Clearly $\Gamma(n) = \Gamma(n^{p-1})$.
 $\therefore F(\Gamma(n^{p-1})) = \Gamma_0(n^{p-1})$ where $\Gamma_0(n^{p-1}) = \{x \in X / n^{p-1} \notin X\}$
 But $\Gamma_0(n^{p-1})$ is a basic open set in X
 $\therefore F$ is a homeomorphism.

Since X is a totally compact Hausdorff automata space, Π is a totally compact Hausdorff automata space.

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